

***ortho*-Aminophenylhydrazine and Some Interesting Heterocyclic Compounds derived from It.**

Part II.

Synthesis of Azoles, Azines, Heptazines and Octazines.

BY

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o-Aminophenylhydrazine was prepared in this laboratory last year by Guha and Ray and its actions upon benzaldehyde, potassium ethyl xanthate, urea, mustard oils, etc., were studied (this *Journal*, 1925, 2, 83). With the object of synthesising poly-membered heterocyclic compounds, it has now been condensed with *o*-diketones, monoximes of *o*-diketones, diamines, esters and chlorides of dicarboxylic acids and thiosemicarbazide, and in every case the above expectation has been fully realised.

o-Aminophenylhydrazine reacts with benzil to give 2:3-benzo-5:6-diphenyl-1:4:7-heptatriazine, thus:

Four more hepta-triazine compounds have similarly been obtained from alloxan, isatin, acenaphthaquinone and phenanthraquinone (compare Thiele and Stanger, *Annalen*, 283, 1; Nietzki, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1357; Tauber,

Ber., 1892, 25, 3287; Niementowsky, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3334; Cain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1440; 1920, 117, 1143; Hinsberg, *Annalen*, 292, 245; *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 200; *Annalen*, 237, 340; Marchlewsky and Buraczewsky, *Bull. Acad. Sci., Cracow*, 1900, 374; Schmidt and Soll, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3696). Monoximes of isatin and phenanthraquinone give rise to interesting octa-triazine compounds, thus:

The above reactions differ remarkably from that observed by Schmidt and Glatz (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 276) who observed the elimination of hydroxylamine and water and not two molecules of water as in the present instance.

Two molecules of ammonia escape from one molecule of *o*-phenylenediamine and one molecule of the aminohydrazine with the formation of 2:3:6:7-dibenzo-4:5-dihydro-1:4:5-heptatriazine, thus:

(Compare Pinner, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2358; Fischer and Hepp, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 2791; Arndt and Bielich, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 809; Guha and De, this *Journal*, 1925, 1, 144).

A controversy may arise here, *viz.*, the *imino* instead of the *amino* group of the hydrazine residue might react as well to give rise to a *N*-aminophenazine compound, thus :

But, as the compound does not react with benzaldehyde or mustard oils, the *N*-aminophenazine type of formula has been dispensed with. 1:3:4-Tolylene-diamine and 1:2-naphthylenediamine similarly give a benzo-methylbenzo-heptatriazine and a benzo-naphthoheptatriazine respectively.

Oxalyl chloride yields *o*-phenylene semioxamazide, thus :

Diethyl malonate yields *o*-phenylene-semimalonamazide. (Meyer, *Annalen*, 327, 14, 26; 347, 25, 34; 415, 33, 42).

One molecule of thiosemicarbazide reacts with one molecule of the aminohydrazine with the liberation of two molecules of ammonia forming a compound of

composition $C_7H_8N_4S$ which may be represented by any of the following four formulæ.

The compounds of formulæ (VIc) and (VI d) should be strongly basic, but the product is acidic in nature, forms alkali salts which form lead and mercury mercaptides, and a disulphide. All these facts are in harmony with the formulæ (VIa) and (VIb). But formula (VIb) has been rejected on the ground that the compound does not dissolve in hydrochloric acid and does not form any compound with benzaldehyde.

o-Nitrophenylhydrazine does not appear to possess any capacity to form any closed-ring compound with aldehydes, ketones, amines, esters, etc., as the aminohydrazine. It can, however, form open-chain compounds

with these reagents and the nitro group of the resulting product can be reduced to an amino group which at once creates a possibility for ring-closure.

Acetaldehyde-*o*-nitrophenylhydrazone yields μ -methylbenziminazole on reduction (compare Franzen, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 909; Guha and Ray, this *Journal*, 1925, 1, 193).

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde- and salicylaldehyde-*o*-nitrophenylhydrazones, when reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid, do not yield μ -aminophenyl- and μ -hydroxyphenyl-benziminazoles as might be expected by analogy with the foregoing reaction, but 2:3:7:8-dibenzo-1:5:6-octatriazine and 2:3:7:8-dibenzo-1:5:6-octaoxydiazine are formed, thus :

The reason for assigning formula (VII) to the nitrobenzaldehyde compound is that it does not give any reaction of the amino group. The formula (VIII) has been retained on similar grounds, *viz.*, because it does not respond to any hydroxylic reactions.

Acenaphthaquinone, anthraquinone, α -naphthaquinone and phenanthraquinone give the corresponding mononitrophenylhydrazones and the first one has been utilised for synthesising a seven-membered ring-compound, 2 : 3-benzo-5 : 6-acenaphtho-1 : 4 : 7-heptatriazine, thus :

Benzil differs from the above diketones and forms only the dihydrazone which gets easily oxidised even on exposure to the air, forming diphenyl-dinitrodiphenyl-isotetrazine (?), thus:

(compare Pickel, *Annalen*, 232, 228).

o-Nitrophenylhydrazone of diacetyl monoxime loses one molecule of water when heated in a sealed tube at 100° with alcoholic hydrochloric acid to give 1-*N*-nitrophenyl-3 : 4-dimethyl-osotriazole, thus :

The resulting product is insoluble in alkali showing the absence of any oxime grouping in it; moreover, it gives all

the reactions of an aromatic nitro group showing that the nitro group has not taken any part in this reaction (compare Willgerodt, *J. pr. Chem.*, 71, 404).

Oxalic ester readily forms oxalo-*o*-nitrophenylhydrazide (XII) which was expected to furnish an eleven-membered ring compound on reduction, thus :

but that could not be isolated owing to the fact that it suffered decomposition at the time of concentrating the reduced solution (*vide* Experimental).

o-Phenylenediamine condenses with the nitrohydrazine with the elimination of one molecule of ammonia to form *o*:*o'*-nitroamino-hydrazobenzene, which in its turn loses another molecule of ammonia on reduction to form 2 : 3 : 6 : 7-dibenzo-4 : 5-dihydro-1 : 4 : 5-heptatriazine, thus :

EXPERIMENTAL.

2 : 3-Benzo-5 : 6-diphenyl-1 : 4 : 7-heptatriazine (I).

One gm. of benzil was allowed to react with 1 gm. of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine hydrochloride in 12 c.c. of glacial acetic acid in a sealed tube at 100° for 5-6 hours, when a crystalline solid substance was deposited. It was

thoroughly washed with water under suction pump in order to make it free from the unreacted hydrochloride and was crystallised from acetone or pyridine as white needles melting at 114° . It becomes yellowish on exposure to air and dissolves in hydrochloric acid. (Found : $N=14\cdot24$. $C_{20}H_{16}N_5$ requires $N=14\cdot14$ per cent.).

Benzo-heptatriazine Compound with Alloxan.

One gm. of alloxan was allowed to react with 1 gm. of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine hydrochloride in 12 c.c. of absolute alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride in a sealed tube at 100° for 4 to 5 hours when a yellow crystalline precipitate was found to have settled at the bottom of the tube. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with hot water and was found to be insoluble in all the ordinary organic solvents. It was dissolved in caustic soda, from which it was precipitated by the addition of hydrochloric acid as beautiful yellow crystalline plates, which did not melt even at 300° . (Found : $N=30\cdot77$. $C_{10}H_7O_2N_5$ requires $N=30\cdot56$ per cent.).

Benzo-heptatriazine Compound with Isatin.

It was prepared as the preceding compound and was crystallised from pyridine in shining red leaflets. It is fairly soluble in alcohol and acetone from which it does not crystallise well. It does not melt even at 300° and is insoluble both in acids and alkalis. (Found : $N=24\cdot1$. $C_{14}H_{10}N_4$ requires $N=23\cdot93$ per cent.).

2 : 3-Benzo-5 : 6-acenaphtha-1 : 4 : 7-heptatriazine.

A mixture of 1 gm. of the aminophenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 1 gm. of acenaphthenequinone was heated in a sealed tube with alcoholic hydrogen chloride as usual. The product crystallised from pyridine or

acetone in orange brown needles melting at 180°. It does not dissolve in alkali or in hydrochloric acid. (Found : N=15.82. $C_{18}H_{11}N_3$ requires N=15.61 per cent.).

2 : 3-*Benzo-5 : 6-phenanthra-1 : 4 : 7-heptatriazine*.

The condensation was brought about as in the case of the above compounds. The product was at first crystallised from pyridine and then from acetone in white needles, melting at 220°. It is fairly soluble in alcohol but insoluble in ether and chloroform. It dissolves with difficulty in strong hydrochloric acid. (Found : N=14.35. $C_{20}H_{13}N_3$ requires N=14.24 per cent.).

Phenanthra-o-phenylene-dihydrazone, similarly obtained from the hydrazine hydrochloride and phenanthraquinone monoxime, formed a green precipitate which was crystallised from pyridine in beautiful green needles. It is fairly soluble in alcohol, acetone and acids and melts at 160°. (Found : N=18.2. $C_{20}N_{14}N_4$ requires N=18.06 per cent.).

o-Amidophenylhydrazine and Isatine Monoxime: Formation of Isatin-orthophenylene-dihydrazone (II).

Equal parts of the reactants in glacial acetic acid solution were heated in a sealed tube for 9 hours at 100°. The yellow needles, obtained on cooling, were repeatedly washed with water and finally crystallised from acetone. The compound is soluble in hydrochloric acid and melts at 270°. (Found : N=28.35. $C_{14}H_{11}N_5$ requires N=28.2 per cent.).

2 : 3 : 6 : 7-*Dibenzo-4 : 5-dihydro-1 : 4 : 5-heptatriazine (III).*

An intimate mixture of 1.5 gm. of the amino-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 1 gm. of *o*-phenylenediamine was heated on an oil-bath at 180-200°. Within the course of a few minutes a molten mass was obtained

and ammonia began to evolve with the progress of the reaction. Heating was continued for about 5 hours when the evolution of ammonia ceased. The reaction product was finally powdered and boiled for about 10 minutes with water. The residue was dissolved in strong hydrochloric acid from which it was precipitated by alkali. This operation was repeated several times and finally it was purified from pyridine, m. p. about 300°. (Found : N=21.85. $C_{12}H_{11}N_3$ requires N=21.32 per cent.).

2 : 3-Benzo-6 : 7-methylbenzo-4 : 5-dihydro-1 : 4 : 5-heptatriazine.

This compound was prepared by heating an intimate mixture of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 1 gm. of 1 : 3 : 4-tolylenediamine at 180—200°. After extraction with hot water the residue was purified by dissolving in strong sulphuric acid and precipitating with a large quantity of water. This operation was repeated several times. It was crystallised from pyridine as a black crystalline powder. It is insoluble in almost all other organic solvents, m. p. above 300°. (Found : N=20.45. $C_{13}H_{13}N_3$ requires N=19.89 per cent.).

2 : 3-Benzo-6 : 7-naphtho-4 : 5-dihydro-1 : 4 : 5-heptatriazine.

It was prepared and purified by a similar method. It crystallised from pyridine in beautiful red crystals. It is insoluble in other organic solvents and melts at 146-48°. (Found : N=17.36. $C_{18}H_{13}N_3$ requires N=17.0 per cent.).

o-Phenylene-semioxamazide (IV).

One gm. of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine was gradually added to a nitrobenzene solution of 1 gm. of oxalyl chloride when the reaction commenced at once. To complete the reaction, the mixture was boiled for a few minutes. On concentration a brown precipitate came

out of the solution which was crystallised from nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in almost all other organic solvents, acids and alkalis and does not melt even at 300° . (Found : $N=24.15$. $C_6H_7O_2N_3$ requires $N=23.72$ per cent.).

o-Phenylene-semimalonamide (V).

One gm. of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine hydrochloride, 2 gms. of sodium acetate and 1 gm. of malonic ester with a small quantity of absolute alcohol were heated in a sealed tube for 5-6 hours between 180 and 200° . The contents of the tube, after a thorough washing with water, were crystallised from pyridine in red plates which are insoluble in acids and alkalis, and do not melt even at 300° . (Found : $N=22.3$. $C_9H_9O_2N_3$ requires $N=21.98$ per cent.).

o-Phenylenethiocarbohydrazide (VIa).

An intimate mixture of 4 gms. of thiosemicarbazide and 2 gms. of the aminohydrazine hydrochloride was heated on an oil-bath at $180-200^{\circ}$, when ammonia evolved. The product was powdered, washed with hot water, dissolved in alkali and precipitated by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid as a black precipitate which was insoluble in all ordinary organic solvents and did not melt even at 300° . (Found : $N=31.62$. $C_7H_8N_4S$ requires $N=31.1$ per cent.).

Disulphide.—An excess of iodine solution (in potassium iodide) was added drop by drop to the thio-compound dissolved just in the required quantity of sodium hydroxide solution, when a yellowish crystalline precipitate insoluble in all organic solvents and melting at 125° was obtained. (Found : $N=31.32$; $S=18.2$. $C_{14}H_{14}N_8S_2$ requires $N=31.28$; $S=17.9$ per cent.).

Acetaldehyde-o-nitrophenylhydrazone.

An alcoholic solution of 3 gms. of acetaldehyde was shaken with 1 gm. of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine, when gradually orange-coloured needles came out of the solution. The product was crystallised from pyridine, m. p. 101°. It is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, ether and chloroform. (Found: N=23.52. $C_8H_8O_2N_2$ requires N=23.46 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of μ -Methylbenziminazole.

Two gms. of the above hydrazone were heated with 6 gms. of granulated tin and 50 gms. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. After a few minutes, a clear red solution was obtained which, however, became colourless on further heating. The solution was then largely diluted with water and tin removed by sulphuretted hydrogen. The solution was then evaporated to dryness on the water-bath, the crystalline residue dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and the free base liberated by the addition of ammonia. It was crystallised from alcohol. It is soluble in ether and forms a soluble hydrochloride with hydrochloric acid and melts at 173°. (Found: N=21.30. $C_8H_8N_2$ requires N = 21.21 per cent.).

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde-o-nitrophenylhydrazone.

A mixture of 2 gms. of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine and 2 gms. of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in dilute alcoholic solution was heated under reflux for about 15 minutes, when an orange-coloured precipitate gradually formed in the solution. It was allowed to cool, filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and cold alcohol, and was crystallised from pyridine. It is insoluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform, alkalis and acids and melts at 223°. (Found: N=19.62. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_4$ requires N=19.58 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Hydrazone: Formation of 2:3:7:8-Dibenzo-1:5:6-octatriazine (VII).

The reduction of the above hydrazone was first tried with zinc dust and acetic acid and then with sodium hyposulphite (compare *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2408) but to no purpose. Finally, the action of tin and hydrochloric acid was tried with success. Three gms. of the above hydrazone were heated under reflux with tin and hydrochloric acid. After an hour, a pink-coloured clear solution was obtained which became colourless on further heating. After removing tin, the solution was evaporated to dryness and the crystalline hydrochloride thus obtained gave the free base on the addition of ammonia. It was crystallised from alcohol in shining colourless plates melting at 210°. (Found: N=20.12. $C_{13}H_{11}N_3$ requires N=20.09 per cent.).

Salicylaldehyde-o-nitrophenylhydrazone.

Two gms. of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazone were heated in alcoholic solution with 2 gms. of salicylaldehyde for about 30 minutes under reflux, when a bright red precipitate came out, which increased in quantity on cooling. It was filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, dissolved in cold sodium hydroxide solution, precipitated by hydrochloric acid and was then crystallised from pyridine. It is insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol and it melts at 192°. (Found: N=16.48. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N=16.3 per cent.).

2:3:7:8-Dibenzo-octa-1-oxy-5:6 diazine (VIII).

The method of preparation was the same as that of compound (VII). The hydrochloride crystallised from alcohol in white needles which melted at 145° with decomposition. (Found: N=11.01. [$C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$] HCl requires N=11.3 per cent.).

o-Nitrophenylhydrazone of Acenaphthenequinone.

A hot acetic acid solution of 1 gm. of the nitrohydrazine was added to a boiling acetic acid solution of 1.5 gm. of acenaphthenequinone when a red precipitate was formed. The mixture was boiled for some time under reflux, allowed to cool, filtered and the precipitate was finally crystallised from alcohol or pyridine in beautiful red crystals, which were insoluble in ether, chloroform, acids and alkalis and melted at 244°. (Found: N=13.15. $C_{18}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N=13.2 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Hydrazone: Formation of 2:3-Benzo-5:6-acenaphtha-1:4:7-hepta triazine (IX).

Two gms. of the above hydrazone were heated under reflux with 5 gms. of tin and 30 gms. of strong hydrochloric acid until an orange coloured clear solution was obtained. The solution on cooling gave crystals which were dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and the base precipitated by the addition of ammonia. It was crystallised from acetone in orange brown needles, m. p. 181°, which were found to be identical with the compound obtained by the action of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine on acenaphthenequinone. (Found: N=15.85. $C_{18}H_{11}N_3$ requires N=15.61 per cent.).

o-Nitrophenylhydrazine and Anthraquinone:

Formation of a Monohydrazone.

A mixture of 1.5 gm. of anthraquinone, 1 gm. of the nitrohydrazine and 15 c. c. of alcohol was heated for 12 hours under reflux when a clear solution was obtained. A brownish red amorphous precipitate was formed when the reaction mixture was poured into water. It was filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, dried and finally crystallised from pyridine. It melted at 206-207°. It is soluble in alcohol but not in acids and alkalis.

(Found: N=12.5. $C_{20}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N=12.24 per cent.).

o-Nitrophenylmonohydrazone of α -Naphthaquinone.

One gm. of the nitrohydrazine was heated in alcoholic solution with 1 gm. of α -naphthaquinone for about 2 hours. Dark red crystals came out of the filtered solution on cooling, and a further quantity was obtained by pouring the reaction mixture in water. It is not soluble in any organic solvent excepting alcohol and even from that it could not be obtained in crystalline condition. It is soluble in strong sulphuric acid from which it can be precipitated by the addition of water. It is insoluble in alkali and in hydrochloric acid, and melts at 170° . The yield was about 1 gm. (Found: N=14.8. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N=14.33 per cent.).

o-Nitrophenylmonohydrazone of Phenanthraquinone.

One gm. of the nitrohydrazine and 1.5 gm. of phenanthraquinone were heated in acetic acid solution under reflux for about 15 minutes when an orange-red crystalline precipitate formed in the hot solution. It was cooled and then filtered and the residue was crystallised from pyridine in beautiful red crystals melting at 245° . The yield was about 2 gms. It was insoluble in water and alcohol. (Found: N=12.32. $C_{20}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N=12.24 per cent.).

An Attempt to prepare o-Nitrophenyldihydrazone of Phenanthraquinone.

One gm. of the above hydrazone and 4 gms. of the nitrohydrazine were heated in a sealed tube at 100° with 12 c. c. of absolute alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride for 12 hours. The compound isolated from the reaction mixture melted at 245° and was proved to be the unconverted monohydrazone,

Benzil-o-nitrophenyldihydrazone.

A mixture of 1 gm. of the nitrohydrazine and 1.5 gm. of benzil was heated in acetic acid solution under reflux for an hour. The solution on standing for a few days yielded an orange red crystalline mass which was first crystallised from acetone and then from alcohol. It melted at 156° . (Found: $N=17.55$. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_6$ requires $N=17.5$ per cent.).

Oxidation of the above Dihydrazone: Formation of Diphenyl-dinitrodiphenyl-osotetrazine. (?)

The above dihydrazone was oxidised merely on exposure to the air to give a white amorphous powder. It was insoluble both in alcohol and acetone by which the unreacted dihydrazone was washed away, m. p. 200° with decomposition. (Found: $N=17.62$. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_6$ requires $N=17.57$ per cent.).

o-Nitrophenylhydrazone of Diacetylmonoxime.

One gm. of the nitrohydrazine was heated in dilute alcoholic solution with 0.7 gm. of diacetylmonoxime for about 2 hours under reflux. An orange red precipitate was formed on pouring the solution into water. It was dissolved in dilute caustic soda and precipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid and was finally crystallised from pyridine. It is readily soluble in alcohol and in alkalis; m. p. $221-222^{\circ}$. (Found: $N=23.5$. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3N_4$ requires $N=23.72$ per cent.).

1-Nitrophenyl-3:4-dimethyl-1:2:5-osotriazole.

One gm. of the above hydrazone was heated in a sealed tube with 12 c. c. of absolute alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride at 100° for 12 hours, when the colour of the solution suffered a gradual change. The brown solid mass, obtained from the contents of the tube, was filtered and crystallised from pyridine. It was insoluble both in acids and in alkalis, sparingly soluble in

alcohol and insoluble in ether. It melted at 285° with decomposition. It gave an azo colour with β -naphthol after the nitro compound was reduced and diazotised. (Found: $N=25.77$. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4$ requires $N=25.68$ per cent.).

Oxalo-o-nitrophenylhydrazide (XII).

A mixture of 1 gm. of oxalic ester and 1 gm. of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid solution was heated for half an hour under reflux when brick-red crystals were found to have deposited which, after filtration and washing, were crystallised from a large quantity of acetic acid; m. p. 265° . It is almost insoluble in all ordinary organic solvents. It dissolves in alkali producing a blue colouration. (Found: $N=23.38$. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6N_6$ requires $N=23.33$ per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound.

One gram of the hydrazide was heated with 6 gms. of tin and 50 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Within an hour, the hydrazide went into solution producing a beautiful pink colouration which was discharged on further heating. Tin was removed from the solution by sulphuretted hydrogen and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the residue was found to be a tarry product.¹

*o-Nitrophenylhydrazine and o-Phenylenediamine:
Formation of o : o'-Nitroaminohydrazobenzene (XIII).*

An intimate mixture of 1.5 gm. of *o*-phenylenediamine and 1 gm. of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine was heated

¹ It is expected that if the evaporation is carried on at a lower temperature under reduced pressure then this sort of decomposition can be avoided. But, unfortunately, the experiment could not be repeated for want of a sufficient quantity of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine.

up to 100°. The whole mass fused and the reaction was allowed to proceed until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The product was ground to a fine powder and boiled with water. The residue was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitated by alkali. This operation was repeated several times. Finally an attempt was made to crystallise it from pyridine but no crystals came out of the solution. It dissolves in acids producing a beautiful red fluorescence and does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N=23.38. $C_{12}H_{12}N_4O_2$ requires N = 22.9 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of 2:3:6:7:-Dibenzo-4:5-dihydro-1:4:5-heptatriazine (IV).

The reduction was carried out in the same way as that of acetaldehyde-*o*-nitrophenylhydrazine. The brown amorphous base was finally crystallised from pyridine, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N=21.8. $C_{12}H_{11}N_3$ requires N=21.32 per cent.). The compound is apparently identical with that obtained by the interaction of *o*-amino-phenylhydrazine and *o*-phenylenediamine (*vide* p. 49).

The work is in progress.

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